

Paste your Photograph Here

Paste your Logo here

Title: Bayes is on the way

Name: Guichong Li

Affiliation: University of Ottawa

email:guichong_li@hotmail.com, contact number: 5167215840

INTRODUCTION:

Thomas Bayes published two works but not including one that bears his name Bayes' Theorem in his lifetime. But Bayes' theorem makes a great impact on all aspects in computation of science and technology. It is believe that this impact incredibly will last forever. Bayesian adherents keep curiosity although many algorithms have been proposed to build Bayesian models such as Bayesian networks, Dynamic Bayesian networks (DBN), etc, according to Bayes' Theorem. In this talk, we focus on a simple Naive Bayes (NB), which holds a well-known assumption of conditional independence among variables. Since NB has exhibited state of the art performance, practitioners have made great effort to enhance NB to overcome poor performance in complex distributions as far as the characteristics of NB remain. Our recent research even goes further where people haven't been there. Straightforward, we develop a new learning algorithm to build a NB to be a non-linear classifier, and the training time of this NB classifier is in a linearity of time complexity. This new research result might show the potential of NB as a general learning methodology for many practical domains. While this new story about NB is taking place, Bayes is never far away from us, and is on the way coming around us.

AIM:

To develop a new learning algorithm to enhance Naive Bayes for either linear or non-linear tasks on complex distributions with a linearity of time complexity

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The main parameters of NB are class conditional probabilities, which can be estimated independently for each class, and then posterior probability distributions are used for classification. The proposed learning algorithm is to produce new training sample by labeling training error as new classes added to the training set with replacement, and the training is repeated until a termination criterion is satisfied. As a result, the posterior probability distribution is estimated from all classes consisting of those original and generated classes.

RESULTS:

The new NB classifier built by using this new learning algorithm is still a linear classifier but for either a linear or a nonlinear tasks while the training time remain linear. Our experimental results show that a new method consistently improves NB in all cases, and thus is expected to be used as a more general learning methodology for various domains.

CONCLUSIONS:

We develop a new learning method to build a NB classifier for either linear or nonlinear learning tasks. As a result, Naive Bayes actually can easily overcome poor performance in some complex domain, and potentially become a more general method for wide applications.

KEYWORDS:

Bayes Theorem, Naive Bayes, conditional independence assumption, non-linear classifier, linear time complexity

BIOGRAPHY:

Guichong Li completed his PhD in 2010 from Computer science of University of Ottawa and two postdoctoral studies in DRDC of National Defense of Canada, and University of Ottawa. He is a machine learning data scientist, recently in NPD Group, NY, USA, for marketing research; a senior machine learning specialist, previously in TellSpec, Toronto, Canada, for biotechnology. He has published more than 10 papers in relevant conferences and workshops, and also holds a US patent for a new MCMC technique for sampling social networks.